

North Macedonia's ERA Integration

Progress and recommendations

Progress

Structural reforms in the research sector

- Publication of Research Infrastructure Roadmap by the Regional Cooperation Council (2022)
- Initiation of the first EIT Community Regional Innovation Scheme Hub
- Expansion of international cooperation activities, advancement of high-quality higher education and intensification of research activities of the National Council on Higher Education and Scientific and Research Activities
- Almost tripled budget of the Annual Programme for R&D Activities in 2022 in comparison to 2021
- Wide recognition of Open Access at universities and broad support for Open Access publications
- Finalisation of Smart Specialisation Strategy

Cooperation between science and industry

- Successful operation of the Fund for Innovation and Technological Development
- Launch of the medium-term work programme 2021-2023 by the Fund for Innovation and Technological Development to strengthen academia-industry cooperation
- Finalisation of the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process within the Smart Specialisation Strategy development (2022)
- Strengthened science-industry cooperation within business accelerators, technology transfer centres, fab labs and innovation hubs

Gender equality

- Adoption of the National Strategy on Equality and Non-Discrimination 2022-2026
- Good representation of women in higher education and the research sector (including grade A and C positions)
- Contribution of the National Platform for Women Entrepreneurship to gender equality

Recommendations

Establish a comprehensive R&D approach

- Develop an integral strategy with more effective measures to improve the quality of human resources for R&D
- Adopt a Smart Specialisation Strategy in 2023 to use innovation and R&D funds more efficiently
- Introduce an appropriate internationalisation strategy and a roadmap

Increase internationalisation activities

- Create more bilateral cooperation programmes
- Establish active participation in ERA meetings
- Engage in the new European Innovation Agenda

Further improve cooperation between academia and industry

- Encourage the private sector to increase its R&D, innovative and investment activities
- Better integrate academia-industry cooperation with more financial resources
- Support knowledge transfer measures